

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT	DD	MM.MMM	LONG	DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2022	08	11	Banjul (Gambia)	N	13	26.554	W	16	34.409
End	2022	08	16	Banjul (Gambia)	N	13	26.554	E	16	34.409

SCIENTIFIC INTEREST & CAMPAING OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the cruise in Gambia river are (i) to observe the changes in microbial life in the river-sea continuum and (ii) to evaluate plastic pollution in the river at its relations with microbes. This work was done in the context of the Microbiome project (2020-2022) that focus on the functional role of the microbial life in the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans.

The research vessel Tara sampled several rivers in South America (including the Amazon) and West Africa during the Microbiome project, providing an opportunity to assess microbiomes and plastics connectivity between rivers and the Atlantic Ocean. Gambia river (Leg 16) is the second river sampled in Africa, after the Orange river (sampled in June 2022) and before Senegal river (planned in September 2022).

PARTICIPANTS

ROLE		NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	Baptiste Regnier (Tara Ocean Foundation)
2	CREW - 1st Officer	Léo Boulon (Tara Ocean Foundation)
3	CREW - Mecano	Laurent Rogniaux (Tara Ocean Foundation)
4	CREW - Deck	Mathieu Oriot (Tara Ocean Foundation)
5	CREW - Deck	François Aurat (Tara Ocean Foundation)
6	CREW - Cook	Carole Pire (Tara Ocean Foundation)
7	CREW - Media	Guillaume Tauran (Tara Ocean Foundation)
8	GUEST - Artist	Irène
9	GUEST - Observer	NFamara B.M Jarju (Gambia Maritime Administration)
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	Noé (IFREMER)
11	SCIENCE - B - W-Lab biogeochemistry	David Leistenschneider (Sorbonne University)
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	Karine Lebaron (Plastic@Sea)
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	Jean-François Ghiglione (CNRS)
14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	Miléna Cerda (Plastic@Sea)

ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT & SAMPLING STRATEGY

Sampling stations are depicted in Figure 1 :

- GAMBIA-01 (station 152) : it is the reference marine station in front of the Gambia river, but away from the river plume. It has been sampled on 2022-08-09 by previous participants (see the last CSR).
- GAMBIA-02 (station 153-a and 153-b) : it is the estuarine station, close to Banjul city. It has been sampled at the same location on 2022-08-11 for station 153-a (from low to high tide) and on 2022-08-12 for station 153-b (from high to low tide).
- GAMBIA-03 (station 154-a and 154-b) : it is station with intermediate salinity (around 16), close to Tendebea city. It has been sampled at the same location on 2022-08-12 for station 154-a (from low to high tide) and on 2022-08-13 for station 154-b (from high to low tide).
- GAMBIA-04 (station 155) : it is the station with null salinity (freshwater), below to Kaur city. It has been sampled on 2022-08-14 with 2 zodiac.
- GAMBIA-05 (station 156) : it is the station with null salinity(freshwater), above to Kaur city. It has been sampled on 2022-08-14 with 2 zodiac.

Figure 1. Location of sampling stations during the Leg 16.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS

All the work initially planned in Gambia river has been achieved. Because the SineGambia bridge did not allowed the research vessel Tara to go further into the river, we used two zodiac to reach the station 155 and 156 (around 30 miles from the SineGambia bridge, where we decided to anchor Tara). A clear salinity gradient was already visible between Banjul and SineGambia bridge, and we sampled freshwater in Kaur (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Change in salinity between Banjul (estuarine waters - station 153) and Balingho (intermediate salinity waters - station 154) in the Gambia river measured by the thermosalinometer onboard the R/V Tara. Note that zero salinity (freshwater) was measured by a manual refractometer around Kaur (stations 155 & 156 – not shown).

We have found so many debris in the sampling site on the river bank close to Tendebe city (station 154) that we stopped sorting the debris (around 15 kg) after only 10m-transect for the OSPAR protocol (instead of the usual 100m transect). Debris were composed of a lot of clothes, ropes and fishing nets. It has been difficult to find appropriated sampling station for the OSPAR protocol, since most of the river banks were composed of mangrove that rendered sampling impossible. Rapid observation showed few macroplastic pollution in the mangrove, which covered most of the river bank in the sampling zone (from Banjul to Kaur). Interestingly, we found relatively few microplastics when sampling in the river with a manta net (Figure 3). We suggest a preliminary conclusion of high pollution by macroplastic debris localized closed to the cities with few extension to the mangrove, and a relatively low microplastic pollution of the Gambia river. Further analysis by the partners of the Microbiome project are needed to confirm this observation and to evaluate how much plastic pollution is related to the transport of invasive or pathogen species in the Gambia river and in the Atlantic sea. Relationships between plastic pollution and the dynamic of the environmental parameters along the river-sea continuum (salinity, nutrients, biogeochemistry,...) together with the microbial life in the surrounding waters will also be investigated.

Figure 3. Image of the zodiac used to reach stations 155 & 156 close to Kaur (left) and image of the cod-end attached to the Manta net showing a small piece of plastic surrounded by branches and leafs (right).

Figure 4. Collecting (left) and sorting (right) of macro-, meso- and microplastics on the river bank close to Tendeba city.

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

Sampling was performed in growing and decreasing tides for station 153 and 154 (labeled a and b, respectively). Sampling was done on the research vessel Tara, but also with its zodiac (for station 155 and 156, above the SineGambia bridge). The same parameters were measured in all stations, except for surface NET WPII20 and WPII200 that sink to the river floor when using zodiac (not sampled for stations 155 and 156). BowPole protocol was done only once per location.

Station ###	Date, start YYYY-MM-DD	Latitude, start N dd.dddddd	Longitude, start E ddd.dddddd	UDW - Aerosols	UDW - Biogeochemistry	BGC – CAST – 0-1000	SML	SRF – PUMP	SRF – NET – WPII 20	SRF – NET – WPII 200	SRF – NET – Manta 330	EPI – CAST – 0-200	EPI – NET – WPII 20	EPI – NET – WPII 200	EPI – Régent 680	MESO – CAST – 0-1000	CAST – Trace Metals	VMP – Profile	TIA – Towed Array	BowPole	hTSRB
153-a	2022-08-11	N13°28.081	W16°32.124	1				1	1	1	1									1	
153-b	2022-08-12	N13°27.755	W16°32.715	1				1	1	1	1										
154-a	2022-08-12	N13°26.376	W15°47.609	1				1	1	1	1									1	
154-b	2022-08-13	N13°26.760	W15°47.708	1				1	1	1	1										
155	2022-08-14	N13°40.128	W15°21.299	1				1	1	1	1									1	
156	2022-08-14	N13°41.421	W15°18.123	1				1	1	1	1										

Table 1. Overview of sampling activities on every day of the Campaign, indicating the number of deployments done for each type of event

STATION EVENTS

- **Station Label: 153-a**

Description: Estuary of the Gambia river close to Banjul city (from high to low tide)

Date: 2022-08-11

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
		A20 pump	0-3	SRF	1				
17:40	17 min	Rosette	0-3	surface	1			1	1
20:04	11 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
20:51	2 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
18:50	20 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
17:23	1 min	Bow Pole	0					1	1

- **Station Label: 153-b**

Description: Estuary of the Gambia river close to Banjul city (from low to high tide)

Date: 2022-08-12

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
00:00	24h	Underway pump	0-3	SRF	1				
00:02	3 min	Rosette	0-3	SRF	1			1	1
00:42	8 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
01:05	2 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
01:17	21 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1

- **Station Label: 154-a**

Description: Intermediate salinity in the Gambia river close to Tendeba city (from high to low tide)

Date: 2022-08-12

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
		A20 pump	0-3	SRF	1				
17:33	5 min	Rosette	0-3	SRF	1			1	1
18:28	5 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
18:01	5 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
19:00	16 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1

- **Station Label: 154-b**

Description: Intermediate salinity in the Gambia river close to Tendeba city (from low to high tide)

Date: 2022-08-13

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
		A20 pump	0-3	SRF	1				
15:05	3 min	Rosette	0-3	SRF	1			1	1
15:52	4 min	WP11 200 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
15:26	2 min	WP11 20 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
16:09	20 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
18:23	10 min	Bow Pole	0					1	1

- **Station Label: 155**

Description: Zero salinity (freshwater) in the Gambia river below Kaur city (no influence of tide)

Date: 2022-08-14

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
11:35	22 min	Carboys 20L-100L	0-3	SRF				1	1
11:47	23 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1
11:21	3 min	Bow Pole	0					1	1

- **Station Label: 156**

Description: Zero salinity (freshwater) in the Gambia river above Kaur city (no influence of tide)

Date: 2022-08-14

Time UTC	Duration	Event	Depth(s)	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
13:09	21 min	Carboys 20L-100L	0-3	SRF				1	1
13:02	18 min	Manta 330 net	0-3	SRF horizontal				1	1

OSPAR protocols on beach and river banks

Date	Time UTC	Duration	Event	Comment	A	B	C	D	E
2022-08-09	15:00	60 min	OSPAR	Beach (Monkey Park Banjul)		1	1	1	1
2022-08-13	10:15	28 min	OSPAR	River bank (Tendebe city)		1	1	1	1
2022-08-14	10:25	25 min	OSPAR	River bank (Kaur city)		1	1	1	1
2022-08-16	15:25	25 min	OSPAR	River bank (Banjul city)		1	1	1	1

S20-L	5-mL-falcon									4			
PM-HG20	Zip-lock												
MB20	4-mL-Vial									4			
CP50	petri-slide									4			
SCP50	petri-slide												
F200	250-mL-bottle												
E200	15-mL-falcon									4			
S200	5-mL-cryotube												4
S200-L	5-mL-falcon									4			
PM-HG200	Zip-lock												
MB200	4-mL-Vial									4			
CP200	petri-slide												
F680	250-mL-bottle												
F2000	250-mL-bottle												
E680	15-mL-falcon												
S680-L	MULTIPLATES												
E2000	15-mL-falcon												
AI	petri-slide	7											
AS	2-mL-cryotube												7
AF	Zip-lock							7					
SP300	2-mL-cryotube												17
MP300	2-mL-cryotube												
CP300	petri-slide	7											
TOC	30-mL-bottle												
SSML-PC	2-mL-cryotube												
SSML-PT	2-mL-cryotube												
S025-L	15-mL-falcon							6					
S520-L	5-mL-falcon									12			
FM5	5-mL-falcon									12			
TOTAL	349	20	3	18			12	82	28	52	60	41	33